

Left atrial segmentation combining multi-atlas whole heart labeling and shape-based atlas selection

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Abstract. Segmentation of the left atria (LA) from late gadolinium enhanced magnetic resonance imaging (LGE-MRI) is challenging since atrial borders are not easily distinguishable in the images. We propose a method based on multi-atlas whole heart segmentation and shape modeling of the LA. In the training phase we first construct whole heart LGE-MRI atlases and build a principal component analysis (PCA) model able to capture the high variability of the LA shapes. All atlases are clustered according to their LA shape using an unsupervised clustering method which additionally outputs the most representative case in each cluster. All cluster representatives are registered to the target image and ranked using conditional entropy. A small subset of the most similar representatives is used to find LA shapes with similar morphology in the training set that are used to obtain the final LA segmentation. We tested our approach using 80 LGE-MRI data for training and 20 LGE-MRI data for testing obtaining a Dice score of 0.842 ± 0.049 .

Keywords: Left atrial segmentation · Multi-atlas segmentation · Atlas selection · LGE-MRI segmentation

1 Introduction

Atrial fibrillation (AF) is the most frequent type of arrhythmia affecting around 1% to 2% of the worldwide population (approximately 33 million in 2015). Prevalence of AF doubles with each decade of age and the AF incidence is rapidly growing with the increasing life expectancy in developed countries [1, 13].

Inspection of LA anatomy in clinical routine often involves LA segmentation which is typically done by fusing several manual segmentations. This is the most accurate method nowadays but automatic segmentation is desirable in order to reduce the high workload and to eliminate inter- and intra-observer variability attributable to manual segmentation. However, accurate automatic segmentation of the LA is challenging due to the high variability of atrial shapes: global features such as size and sphericity, and local features such as number,

position and orientation of the pulmonary veins (PVs), and size and shape of the left atrial appendage (LAA) greatly differ between patients. Most of patients have 4 PVs (up to 70%) but it is relatively frequent to have a common left trunk (around 15 %) or one or even two extra right PVs [8]. The LAA size and shape could be even more arbitrary [5].

Some methods have been able to successfully segment the LA in an automatic or semi-automatic way using different image modalities [3, 12, 11, 2]. LA automatic segmentation is especially challenging in LGE-MRI data due to the intrinsic characteristics of this image modality. LGE-MRI is used to visualize and quantify the extent of fibrosis (or scar) in the chambers of the heart. The contrast agent appears enhanced (white) in fibrotic areas while the myocardium is nulled in the rest facilitating the detection of scar but at the same time complicating the delineation of the cardiac substructures. In the case of the LA, the healthy (non-fibrotic) parts of the thin atrial wall exhibit a very similar intensity profile to the surrounding structures (e.g. the left ventricle).

Multi-atlas segmentation (MAS) has been widely used in different clinical contexts [6]. The outline of MAS involves registering N atlases (labeled images) to a given target image and derive the final segmentation by applying label fusion. Many methods have been proposed for the different steps (mainly registration and label fusion) and when the number of available atlases is increased the pipeline often involves atlas selection, i.e. selecting the most appropriate set of atlases and discarding the rest [10]. Ideally, atlas selection needs to be done before the registration step to avoid unnecessary computational costs of registering bad atlases that marginally contribute to the final segmentation [7]. On the other hand, this strategy is not optimal neither since registration quality should have a role on atlas selection (e.g. better registration quality for a given atlas). Most MAS schemes rely on registration to a common reference space where similarity metrics can be computed. However, when the population of images shows large variability in appearance and shape it becomes arduous to come up with a unique template that is representative of all the rest. As mentioned before, different LAs often do not even have the same parts (i.e. different number of PVs) and for example, a LA with an extra right PV will not be well represented using a template image with 4 PVs. Thus registration between LAs with varying topology becomes problematic.

In the absence of a suitable common reference space and to avoid a high number of pairwise registrations, we propose to group the training dataset by the corresponding LA morphology, determined from the LA shape. When a new target image has to be segmented, the images from the training set representative of each morphology cluster are registered to the target to identify the correct morphology of the target. Once the morphology is known, the segmentation is carried out via multi-atlas framework using only the atlases corresponding to this morphology. We tested our method using the dataset provided by the organizers of the 2018 Atrial Segmentation Challenge (STACOM'18⁴). It comprises 100 3D

⁴ <http://atriaseg2018.cardiacatlas.org/>

Fig. 1. Scheme of the proposed pipeline. The cluster representative is depicted enhanced. MAS-WHS = Multi-atlas whole heart segmentation; PDM = Point distribution model; PCA = Principal component analysis; AA = Aux atlases; GA = Global atlases; SA = Specific atlases.

MRI patient data acquired using a clinical whole-body MRI scanner and the corresponding LA manual segmentations.

2 Methodology

The pipeline of the proposed method can be seen in Figure 1. We built our method from the multi-atlas whole-heart segmentation (MAS-WHS) technique presented in [14] and [16] since the joint segmentation of surrounding structures may help in identifying the structure limits. Briefly, in the registration step of the MAS-WHS strategy all atlases were registered to the target image using a hierarchical scheme designed for cardiac images: first, a global affine registration was performed followed by a three-level locally affine registration (LARM) [15] to initialize substructure alignment, and by a non-rigid registration based on free-form deformations (FFD) [9] to refine local details. We considered seven substructures: left and right ventricular cavities, right atrial cavity, left atria (considering the cavity, the PVs and the LAA), the left ventricular myocardium, the ascending aorta and the pulmonary artery. For the label fusion step we applied atlas ranking based on conditional entropy [14] and a patch based strategy [16].

To obtain labels of the remaining substructures (i.e. derive whole heart LGE-MRI atlases) we first performed MAS-WHS using the 30 high-resolution balanced steady state free precession (bSSFP) volumetric MRI atlases distributed

by the Left Atrial Segmentation Challenge (STACOM'13) [12]. Due to the intrinsic differences between the two image modalities (LGE-MRI and bSSFP MRI for target and atlases, respectively) the automatic MAS-WHS results were poor for many cases. For that reason we re-segmented all cases applying again MAS-WHS using a new atlas set, Aux Atlas (AA), built selecting the best 15 results obtained in the initial step and replacing the LA automatic segmentation by the ground truth provided by the STACOM'18 challenge.

To group together images with similar LA shapes we first extracted all LA surfaces from the ground truth segmentations by applying the marching cubes algorithm. After that, we characterized each atrial mesh using a point distribution model (PDM) obtained by consistently sampling the LA surface meshes defining rays from the LA center of mass in all directions. We used spherical coordinates, (r, ϕ, θ) , to define the rays with $r = 100$, high enough to intersect the LA shape, $\phi \in [0, \pi]$ with $\phi/70$ step and $\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$ with a variable number of samples for each ϕ increasing from 1 to 70 and decreasing again to 1. We proceed like that to have more points in the areas where LA shapes are wider. In that way, the final number of points representing each shape was 2452. The LA shapes were then characterized by the intersection points between the rays and the surface. When the ray intersected more than once (because of the PVs) only the furthest intersecting point was considered. We computed the mean PDM and aligned all the PDMs to the mean using iterative closest point (ICP). Finally, we applied PCA to reduce the dimensionality of the data and clustered the shapes using the Affinity Propagation method [4]. This method clusters data by iteratively identifying a subset of representative examples and assigning the remaining elements to a specific representative when the method converges. Let us call the set of N cluster representatives global-atlases (GA). Ideally, the GA set contains a good representation of highly variable atrial shapes.

To segment an unseen target image we proceeded as follows: we first registered the GA to the target image using the hierarchical registration scheme commented before [14]. We then ranked all atlases according to the negative conditional entropy of the target image (I) given the warped label image (L_n) which corresponds to:

$$-H(I|L_n) = \sum_{i \in I, l \in L_n} p(i, l) \log \frac{p(i, l)}{p(l)} \quad (1)$$

where H is entropy, $p(i, l)$ is the joint probability of the intensity value i and label l , and $p(l)$ is the marginal probability of label l . We then selected the P global atlases with highest negative conditional entropy and found the S closest shapes in PCA space to each of the P GA. The set of $M = P \times S$ atlases defined a target-specific set of atlases (SA) used to derive the final LA segmentation in a MAS framework.

Fig. 2. All cluster representatives (left) and examples of small clusters showing all pertaining shapes superimposed (right). Representatives are sorted according to the first principal component that was identified as size/sphericity. RSPV = Right Superior PV, RIPV = Right Inferior PV, LSPV = Left Superior PV, LIPV = Left Inferior PV, LAA = Left Atrial Appendage.

3 Experiments and Results

We used data from the 2018 Atrial Segmentation Challenge (STACOM’18) to test our method. The dataset was randomly split into training and testing sets (80 and 20 cases, respectively) and, consequently, 80 LGE-MRI whole heart atlases were constructed. PDMs were built using 2452 rays, which was experimentally found appropriate to capture atrial anatomy, and a PCA model describing the LA shape variability in the training set was obtained. We decided to keep the 34 first principal components since they correspond to the 95% of cumulative variance. Fifteen representative shapes were identified by applying the Affinity Propagation clustering method and the GA was built using the corresponding atlases. The mean number of samples in each cluster was 5.33 ± 3.94 ranging from only 1 to 14. The 15 shape representatives can be seen in Fig. 2 as well as some of the clusters found. Our shape-based clustering method was able to identify a duplicated sample which was eliminated from the dataset. We decided to keep the $P = 3$ best GA as shape representatives and search for the $S = 5$ samples closest to each representative. We therefore constructed the SA with only 15 atlases.

To test segmentation accuracy we used three metrics: Dice similarity defined as

$$Dice(X, Y) = 2 \frac{|X \cap Y|}{|X| + |Y|} \quad (2)$$

surface to surface distance, defined as

$$S2S(S, T) = mean(d(S, T), d(T, S)) \quad (3)$$

and Hausdorff distance defined as

$$HD(S, T) = max(d(S, T), d(T, S)) \quad (4)$$

Fig. 3. From left to right: Dice score, surface to surface distance and Hausdorff distance. All distances are reported in mm. Results corresponding to the different sets of atlases considered are shown: AA = Aux Atlases, GA = Global Atlases, SA_s = Specific Atlases found using the preliminary shape, SA = Specific Atlases selected using the proposed approach.

Table 1. LA segmentation results: Dice, surface to surface distance (S2S) and Hausdorff distance (HD) corresponding to the different experiments.

	AA	GA	GA + SA _s	SA _s	GA + SA	SA
Dice	0.807 ± 0.076	0.797 ± 0.122	0.819 ± 0.094	0.828 ± 0.065	0.838 ± 0.075	0.842 ± 0.049
S2S	3.675 ± 1.892	3.553 ± 3.014	3.209 ± 2.231	2.820 ± 1.262	2.843 ± 1.768	2.630 ± 1.124
HD	30.456 ± 16.114	27.442 ± 12.831	26.806 ± 12.215	24.704 ± 8.383	26.014 ± 9.561	24.041 ± 8.141

where X and Y are the automatic and reference segmentation, respectively, S and T the set of voxels in the boundary of X and Y , respectively, and d is the Euclidean distance.

We compared our shape-based atlas selection approach with the performance obtained using other atlas sets. As baseline we used the results from the MAS-WHS performed using AA. We also derived a preliminary segmentation using the GA since those atlases were already fully registered to the target image in a previous step. We applied label fusion and obtained a preliminary LA segmentation whose related LA surface mesh was then sampled and projected to PCA space. The closest shapes were selected and a new set of target-specific atlases (SA_s) was established. We decided to keep the 15 closest shapes to have same atlas size as in our proposed approach. We investigated if including the highly variable (in terms of LA shape) global atlases, i.e. GA, was beneficial or disadvantageous.

As can be seen in Fig. 3 and Table 1 the best configuration corresponded to solely using the SA. The worse performance corresponded to the use of GA, and whenever the GA was used jointly with the specific atlases SA or SA_s the results got worse than using only the latter.

4 Discussion

Results show that the highly variable GA was not able to produce accurate segmentations. This could be understood since if the atlas set is very diverse only

few atlases will positively contribute to segment each target image, i.e. the number of useful atlases is actually small. Even if in the label fusion step the weight of bad atlases is low, they would still negatively contribute to the segmentation. We found 2 clusters with only 1 representative which means that their shape was so specific that could not be grouped together with other samples. Due to the relatively low accuracy of segmentations with GA, the preliminary shapes were inaccurate and quite similar between them. This was also revealed by the fact that after sampling, all corresponding PDMs were very similar, projections to PCA space fell close together and the SA_s was (apart from the order) the same in most cases.

However, we found that registering GA to the target image and ranking the atlases according to the negative conditional entropy helped to position the target in PCA space and in that way infer shape features such as size or number of PVs. Then, for refinement, we decided to keep $P = 3$ best GA and look for similar shapes using Euclidean distance in PCA space. We decided to keep several cluster representatives to reduce the influence of atlas ranking errors and to relatively increase the shape variability of the final atlas set. Restricting ourselves to one cluster may increase the risk of failing if the atlas ranking or the shape-based clustering is not accurate. We could use other criteria to include similar shapes in SA such as all samples in the P clusters but we decided to use Euclidean distance in PCA space because of the different cluster size (from 1 to 14) and because we aimed to have the same number of atlases for all targets to have comparable computational time for all cases. We also based our decision of having a final set of 15 SA on the computational time. Using 3 representatives and 5 related atlases was experimentally found to provide the best compromise between accuracy and computational time but it still needs validation and would probably need to be adjusted depending on the training set (i.e. number of clusters found and samples in each cluster).

Most atlas selection methods require non rigid registration between the target image and the atlases. To reduce the computational cost of such high number of registrations some methods perform offline atlas to atlas registration in order to cluster similar atlases together. Compared to those methods our shape based atlas ranking reduces the number of non-rigid registrations required.

5 Conclusions

In this paper we have shown that atlas selection is an important step in MAS and we have proposed a two-step strategy to identify the most appropriate set of atlases for segmenting highly variable structures such as the LA. We showed that a simple sampling approach was able to capture LA morphology and could be used to automatically group together similar shapes. Shape information could be therefore used to discard bad atlases prior to registration avoiding a high number of computationally expensive registrations and improving segmentation results.

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